

Linguistic-Cultural Study of the domain "Zhylqy" (horse) in the Kazakh Context

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ABSTRACT: This article presents a cultural-linguistic study of the horse terms in the Kazakh language. The consideration of Horse terms allowed us to argue that this domain represents a highly informative semantic system with all its peculiarities. The importance of the horse in the everyday life of the Kazakh people necessitated a communicative need to distinguish between the many properties and qualities of this animal, and, accordingly, there are many terms for stages of their age, productivity/non-productivity in terms of reproductive capacity and milk yield, behavioral characteristics of female species, speed characteristics of male species, etc. The communicative need affects the structure of the lexicon as a whole. Each term is used to communicate informatively about the animal. Our research has enabled us to find out which features of horses are most significant for the linguistic consciousness of the Kazakhs. By giving multiple names to the same animal "Zhylqy" the Kazakhs demonstrated their special responsibility for this animal's welfare throughout its life and emphasized its unique importance in their lives.

Key words: Horse terminology, Communicative need, Informativeness, Communicative efficiency, Lexical precision

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1. Introduction

The object of this research is the consideration of the horse nomenclature in the Kazakh language, namely, lexical-semantic field of horse terms proper (LSF) "Zhylqy" (Horse). Horse terminology is useful research material for comprehension of how the Kazakh language divides this aspect of Kazakh life into words and meanings. The research of LSF "Zhylqy" will help to penetrate into the conceptual world view of the Kazakhs and to find out how this domain of life of the Kazakhs is reflected in the language, why and for what reasons the Kazakh language is rich in horse terminology. Since every community employs language for the purpose of communication and naming is determined primarily by people's practical and communicative needs, the study of the zoonyms "Zhylky" (horse) will allow us to determine which features of horses are most significant for the linguistic consciousness of the Kazakhs.

Borkfelt (2011) proposed an interesting idea that the act of naming can have various consequences for what is named. According to the author, the act of naming is one of the most fundamental acts of language, and when man gives names to animals, he actually exercises power over them and "through the act of naming animals, humans acknowledge their responsibility to them".

The LSF "Zhylyky" research is also very interesting in terms of the principles of communicative efficiency and communicative need. Karjus et al. (2021) state that when a language community has a strong need to differentiate concepts in a specific topic or area of vocabulary, the preference for simplicity may be overridden in order to minimize ambiguity. This results in increased informativeness but also increased complexity. Conversely, if a particular domain is less important to a community, it may be simplified, which can lead to a higher risk of communication errors.

The idea of informativeness and simplicity was widely discussed in the works by Gibson et al. (2017), Kemp et al. (2018), Regier et al. (2018), and Zaslavsky et al. (2019). They argue that a maximally informative semantic system would have a separate word for each object in a given semantic domain – e.g. a separate colour term for each distinguishable hue – which would be complex and unwieldy. In contrast, a maximally simple system would have just one word for all objects in a given semantic domain – e.g. a single color term for all colors – and this would not support precise communication. The vocabularies of the domains characterized by the communicative principles of informativeness exhibit high level of lexical precision in all languages. A highly informative communicative system would be very fine-grained, detailed, and explicit – and would as a result be complex, not simple. The authors illustrate this case by showing the concept pairs SNOW and ICE that are more likely to have distinct word forms in the languages spoken in regions of cooler climate due to greater needs for expressing and distinguishing them (Regier et al., 2016). Similar work has also shown how communicative need may shape lexical precision within an individual domain such as kinship (Kemp and Regier, 2012), i.e., why we do not have a single term that labels MOTHER and FATHER, reflecting the view that semantic domains across languages are structured to support efficient communication (Kemp et al., 2018).

The literature review: The horse has been the subject of research by scholars from different cultures, as the horse has played and continues to play an irreplaceable role in the life of numerous human societies. In each culture, the horse has its "valeur" and is endowed with its own peculiarities determined by the historical past of the people.

In this section we focus on the review of studies by Kazakh scholars: G. Sarbassova (2015), J. Baitelieva (2007), A. Temirbekova, et.al (2022), D.M. Dauletaliyeva, et.al (2020), whose research works were conducted in the context of linguistic and cultural content.

Kazakh scholar G. Sarbassova in her research "Language and Identity in Kazakh Horse Culture" points out that the Kazakhs appeared on the historical stage together with their horses. The horse was a loyal companion and protector, aiding in overcoming economic and military challenges of daily life. While for other peoples horses are just for riding, transport or sport, for the Kazakhs horses are an integral part of their cultural

heritage. The author categorizes the horse as the most significant feature of Kazakh national identity and a symbol of Kazakh culture and prestige. The language part of her paper is devoted to the consideration of linguistic expressions connected with horse culture denoting measurement of time interval, time of the day, month, distance, etc. For example: "*biye sauim uakyt*" – time spent to milking the horse – 30 minutes; "*at shaptyrym zher*" – a distance approximately 25 km; "*biye baylar kez*" – spring time, approximately in May (time when "*biye*" (female horse) is separated from the herd and given a special care and food in order to produce more milk) (G. Sabassova, 2015).

Researches done by J. Baitelieva (2007) and A. Temirbekova, et.al (2022) dwell on the study of the phraseological units and proverbs with the names of horse in the Kazakh language.

J. Baitelieva concludes that the horse names are widely used as part of a big number of the phraseological units. A. Temirbekova, et.al conducted comparative-constructive study of proverbs with horse terms in Kazakh and Turkish languages and discovered that proverbs in both languages contain similar group of lexemes since Kazakh and Turkish languages belong to the same language family, and cultural values have similar linguistic and cultural backgrounds (A. Temirbekova, et.al 2022).

D.M. Dauletaliyeva, et.al have considered the etymological characteristics of horse names; their origin, evolution of their meanings across time, word structure and phonetic particulars. A valuable point of their study is that they did a comparative analysis of the horse names in related languages which help detect the history of their origin. (D.M. Dauletaliyeva, 2020)

This study differs from previous studies in that it focuses on the study of horse terms proper in the Kazakh language. It is assumed that by examining this particular choice of words it will be possible to determine the features of horses that are most significant for the linguistic consciousness of the Kazakhs, how this lexicon reflects their practical needs and interests and the characteristic features of their everyday existence.

The object of our study is the set of horse terms proper "Zhylqy" (horse) in the Kazakh language. The scientific tasks of this research paper are:

- (i) to identify the constituents the LSF of horse terms proper "Zhylqy" (Horse) as the means of linguistic reflection of this fragment of the Kazakh picture of the world;
- (ii) to determine the structural organization of the LSF;
- (iii) to reveal the semantic peculiarities of the lexemes that compose it;
- (iv) to find out which features of horses are most significant for the linguistic consciousness of the Kazakhs.

We believe that this research will be a special case of the general hypothesis that language is shaped by the communicative need for efficient communication – that is informative and precise.

2. Theoretical framework

To carry out this study, the Semantic Field theory and Componential Analysis are fundamental.

2.1 Lexical-Semantic field (LSF)

In our work, we use the term "lexical-semantic field" based on the approach to this concept by Lehrer (1985). In her opinion, a field is a collection of lexemes that cover a specific conceptual domain and have specific relationships to one another. It is important to note that the semantic fields in different languages represent the structural organization of the surrounding world, verbalized by means of a given language. Each semantic field is inherent only to a given language and is able to segment that piece of reality, which it reflects. The set of words covering a certain area in one language is unlikely to correspond to those in any other language. (Aitchison, 2020).

The LSF is singled out by one archyseme – generic, integrating seme, characteristic of lexical units in a semantic field (it is also the name of a semantic field). This seme is present in a semantic structure of every lexical unit in the LSF. Within a semantic field each word has its unique place determined by its semantic relations with other words of the same field. Words can be localized nearer or farther from one another. LSF is characterized by a hierarchical structure, consisting of the: (i) Center/nucleus – name of the field represented by an archyseme which organizes a semantic field deployment around itself; (ii) Near-center zone, including units of a center – integral meaning; (iii) Periphery, consisting of the units most remote in the meaning from the nucleus (Vlasova, 2014). Lexical-semantic fields are not isolated from each other. Every word of the language included in a particular lexical-semantic field, and, due to its polysemantic meaning, can be not only in one but also in several LSF. One semantic field may be included in another field at a higher level.

2.2 Componential analysis

Componential analysis is a *linguistic analysis of the semantic structure of a word (a monosemantic word or a lexico-semantic variant of a polysemantic unit) as constituted by a set of minimal elements of sense – semes*. It reveals the culturally important features by which speakers of the language distinguish different words in a semantic field or domain (Ottenheimer, 2006).

The central term in componential analysis technique is seme. The seme is defined as the minimum limit unit of the content plan. Semes, as constituent components of meaning, differ from each other in their nature and hierarchical status. The semantic structure is the structural organization of the semes that make up the meaning of a certain lexical unit. It consists of an integral and differential semes. An archyseme reflects the generic concept, which encompasses all concepts denoted by the words referring to one semantic field and the integral ones are common for the compared units. The differential seme constitutes the nucleus of the word meaning that determines its scope within the LSF and differentiates the meaning of the given word from the meaning of its neighboring word. Each seme is the reflection in the human consciousness of the differential features that are inherent to the objects of the reality or ascribed to them by the language community.

2.3 Kazakh horse culture

The horse accompanied the Kazakhs in all their life activities. It is now an established fact that horse domestication has begun on the territory of modern Kazakhstan about 5,500 years ago, which is approximately 1,000 years earlier than originally thought. The following evidence serves the proof of this statement: Alan Outram, a British archaeologist from the University of Exeter and his research team had discovered evidence that pushed back the earliest signs of the widespread riding and milking of horses by 1,000 to 2,000 years from previous estimates. They published their research in the October 2009 issue of the prestigious international journal – Science. They excavated the remains of horses from the Botai region of northern Kazakhstan. Radiocarbon dating established that these remains were around 5,500 years old (Outram et al., 2011).

Domestication of the horse was a great breakthrough in the advanced development of nomadic societies. The ability of the horse to cover long distances in a short period of time allowed nomadic people to easily move from place to place and this brought big changes in their culture, with an impact on transportation, defence of their lands from constant attacks of aggressive neighbours which was inconceivable without cavalry. The Kazakh forefathers owe their ability to retain their vast lands to the horse, currently the 9th largest country in the world by territory. For the Kazakh nomad, the horse is the animal, giving him everything - food, clothing, transportation, helper in doing agricultural work, entertainment, the opportunity to hunt and fight. It was and is also an excellent gift and the attribute of prestige and richness. Among all domestic animals, horses occupy a specific place and in everyday life the Kazakhs value the horses above all of them. For Kazakh nomads, they were very practical animals, grazing in herds on the steppe and feeding themselves.

One interesting fact about the horse is as follows: there is an old Kazakh saying – "*drink where the horse drinks*". A horse would, as a rule, try to avoid drinking dirty, muddy or rotten swamp water and eat from an unwashed feeder. Horses usually have specific preferences for the tastes, textures, and smells of the things they ingest. Horses are notable for their selectivity and cleanness; this is the reason why their meat and milk are considered to be specifically nutritious and useful. One more very curious fact about horses is that the stallions of the Kazakh breed "*Zhaby*" do not perceive their "*daughters*" as breeding partners and remember them for a long time even after they leave the herd (Nurushev, 2006).

The image of a horse accompanies a person from his infancy. Kazakh mothers call their children "*Qulynym*" (my foal). The Kazakhs qualify this animal the King of livestock. The reverent attitude of the Kazakhs towards this animal has been preserved to this day.

There are the images of two legendary horses in the state emblem of Kazakhstan. The winged mythical horses – "*Tulpar*" (Pegasus), are the key heraldic element of the State Emblem. The image of the horse stands for such notions as bravery since the time immemorial. The wings symbolize a centuries-old dream of multinational people of Kazakhstan to build a strong and prosperous nation. Today the horse is a symbol of Kazakh

culture and prestige. Horse became Kazakh's national heritage and identity. (Sarbassova, 2015).

According to Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN data Kazakhstan ranks second in the world in terms of horses per capita (202 horses per 1,000 people) after Mongolia (FAO, 2022).

The 13th session of UNESCO, which took place from November 26 to December 1, 2018 in Port Louis, the capital of the Republic of Mauritius, acknowledged Kazakh horse breeders' ceremonies as a legacy of humanity (Smail, 2018).

3. Methodology

3.1 Materials

In the Kazakh language picture of the world, a significant portion of the lexicon pertains to horses and equestrianism. The whole linguistic material on the domain “Zhylqy” in the Kazakh language picture besides horse terms proper encompass the following thematic groups: “Breed”, “Allure”, “Horse equipment”, “Color”, “Body parts”, “Food products made of horse meat”, “Physical characteristics of horses”, “Actions of horses and their behavior characteristics”, “Horse diseases and treatment”, “Horse grazing strategies”, “Proverbs, sayings, metaphorical expressions with the names of horses”. And this is not the end of all the list of knowledge and experience the Kazakhs have accumulated in the course of centuries of horse breeding activities.

The research material for study of the LSF of horse terms proper “Zhylqy” was gathered from the following sources:

- I. A. Baizhumanuly, K. Bekbolatuly, Dictionary of Agricultural Terms, 2012;
- II. N.K. Aitbayeva, The Horse-related names in the Kazakh language, 2007;
- III. Kazakhtyn etnographicalyq ugymdary men ataularynyn dastyrli zhuyesi, Encyclopedia Volume 5, 2014;
- IV. B. Kairatuly, Kazakhtyng atbegilik onery, 2015;
- V. from the mouth of a horse breeder Dauletgeldy who we interviewed on this topic and from the Internet resources.

3.2 Procedure

The main methods for solving the assigned tasks were: method of field structuring of selected linguistic units, analyzing their semantics through application of the method of componential analysis, interpretive and descriptive language research methods. A cultural - linguistic analysis is based on method of correlation of linguistic and cultural phenomena. We also used an interview with a Kazakh horse breeder as part of our research to obtain information that helped us better understand some points of the research topic.

The research included collection of the nomenclature related to LSF “Zhylqy”, distributing of them across the nuclear and peripheral zones of the field, defining their semantic structure and revealing their semantic peculiarities. The construction of the LSF of “Zhylqy”, the analysis of its structure, content and semantic peculiarities allowed us to draw

interesting observations that each term for horses within the LSG “Zhylyq” has its allotted place and its specific meaning. These terms provide a comprehensive reflection of all the functions of this animal which it fulfills and the role it plays in the life of the Kazakhs. They allow to identify which features of horses are most significant for the linguistic consciousness of the Kazakhs.

4. Results

4.1 The constituents, structural organization and semantic structure of the LSF “Zhylyq”

The nucleus/center of the LSF of horse terms proper is an archiseme “Zhylyq” – “a domesticated animal (E-Caballus) of great importance in the economy, grown for the production of meat and *koumiss*, horseback riding, wheelchair or sleigh riding, military and sports areas” which is a dominant generic integrating some characteristic of the semantic structure of all lexical units of the present semantic field and reflects their common categorial properties and features (Dictionary of Agricultural Terms, 2012).

The near center of the LSF “Zhylyq” includes the words that make up the lexical groups joined together by the integral semes: “Zhylyq *tolderi*” (horse youngstocks), “*Biye*” (female horse), “*Aigy*” (stallion, male horse), “*At*” (castrated horse).

We categorize these lexical groups as thematic groups since the horse terms are combined on the basis of direct correlation with real beings. The specific feature of a thematic group is that words in it denote the realities that are not created by human hands or his consciousness. They are natural objects or living beings that exist beyond the will or wish of the people. A thematic group is any set of words of the same lexico-grammatical category, distinguished on the basis of an extralinguistic feature (Khashimov, 2015).

4.1.2 Thematic group “Zhylyq *tolderi*” (horse young stocks)

Thematic group “Zhylyq *tolderi*” (horse young stocks) includes the names of horse offspring between birth to 2 years of age:

Table 1. Thematic group “Zhylyq *tolderi*” (horse young stocks)

Kazakh terms	Differential semes			English terms
	age	male	female	
Kulyyshak	1-1.5 months from birth	-	-	Foal
Kulyyn	From 1.5 month to 6 months	-	-	Foal
Zhabagy	After 6 months up to 1 year	-	-	Weanling/Foal
Tai	Between 1-2 years old	-	-	Yearling/Foal
Arda—the foal sucking mother's milk up till the age 2	Between 1-2 years old foal	-	-	Foal

The semantic structure of each term is composed of integral seme “horse offspring”+differential seme “biological age”.

Kulyyn +shak = horse offspring + a newly born foal of 1-1.5months;

Kulyn=horse offspring+ a foal from 1.5-6 months of age;

Zhabagy=horse offspring+a foal from 6 months to 1 year;

Tai=horse offspring+the age between 1-2years old;

Arda =horse offspring + a foal that was sucking mother's milk up till the age two.

As a rule, foals suck their mother's milk during 5-7 months, so the distinguishing feature of Arda is that this foal doesn't stop sucking its mother's milk up till the age two.

4.2 Thematic group: “*Biye*” (female horse)

Table 2. Thematic group: “*Biye*” (female horse)

Kazakh terms	Semantic structure	English terms
Qunazhyn	horse + female + 2 years old +maiden	Filly
Donezhyn	horse + female + 3years old +maiden	Filly
Baital	horse + female + 3-4 years old +maiden	Filly
Besty biye	horse + female + 5 years old + foaled	Mare
Qysyraq	horse + female + 4-5 years old + non-pregnant	-
Soital	horse + female + 4-5 years old + foaled, but left its foal	-
	horse + female + 4-5 years old +miscarriage or pregnancy failure	
Qoulyq	horse + female + 4-5 years old + foaled for the first time	-
Qasabaly biye	horse + female + 7-8 years old + fertile + high yield of milk	Mare
Sary qaryn biye	horse + female + 9-10 years old + fertile + high yield of milk	Productive Mare
Kartamys biye	horse + female + 10-14 years old	Senior /productive mare
Kary biye	horse + female + 15-16 years old	Aging mare
Zhasagan biye	horse + female + 17-19 years old	Old mare
Laksa biye	horse + female + 20 years old and higher	Aged mare

4.3 Thematic group “*Aigyr*” (male horse,stallion)

“*Aigyr*” is an uncastrated male horse used to lead the herd and for breeding purposes.

The Kazakhs have always practiced and still practice herd horse breeding. Horses are herd animals; they feel relatively safe only in a herd. Kazakh horse breeders believe that animals should not be denied the lifestyle that nature itself has determined (Naimanovet et al., 2018). One of the most responsible tasks of horse breeders in connection with this form of horse husbandry is the selection of a stallion for breeding purposes, as well as the leader of the herd. Among Kazakh horse breeders there is a very old tradition called “*Aigyr qoiu*” - the selection of the stallion that has specific qualities such as the ability to produce healthy offspring, physical strength, stamina, good bloodline and dominant personality. He should also be fast, a good racer, quick and alert. As horse breeding has been a centuries-old occupation of the Kazakhs, there are truly great connoisseurs among horse breeders who could visually assess the quality of stallions that were excellent breeders and powerful leaders of the herd. As the leader of the herd, it is the

role of the dominant stallion to protect and defend the herd in order to keep the herd safe and moving and at the same time perform its breeding function (Naimanov et al., 2018).

Table 3. Thematic group “Aigyr” (male horse, stallion)

Kazakh terms	Semantic structure	English terms
Qunan aigyr	horse + male + 2 years old	Colt
Donen aigyr	horse + male + 3 years old	Colt
Sauryk aigyr	horse + male + 4 years old	Colt
Zhasamaly aigyr	horse + male + 4 -5 years old	Stallion
Sadyr/kosem aigyr	horse + male + a strong, powerful leader of the herd	Stallion
Besty aigyr	horse + male + 5 years old	Stallion
Azban aigyr	horse + male + 6 years old + castrated + shows stallion characters and behavior	
Saqa aigyr	horse + male + 11-12 years old	Aged stallion

In Kazakh horse breeding practice some stallions are castrated later at the age of 4-5 years with the purpose that the horse doesn't lose its power, agility and courage. This type of horses is called “Azban” which is a strong, powerful, masculine horse used by Kazakh warriors – “Batyr” in warfare.

The term “Sauryk” is given to the four years old male horse without his own herd but used as a young breeder. The term “Azban aigyr” means that the male horse was castrated at the age of 6 years and for this reason still shows stallion characters and behavior. The stallions that are strong, dominant, capable of producing good healthy offspring are distinguished by the term “Zhasamaly aigyr”. The stallions, the herd leaders, when come of 11-12 years of age, as a rule, are changed.

4.4 Thematic group “At” (gelding, male horse term)

At the age of 2-2.5 years colts unsuitable for breeding are castrated and they are called by the term “At” in the Kazakh language picture. This biological intervention is intentionally done to adapt the animal for economic needs, sports competitions, racing, fast riding, speedy transportation, and military activities. It ensures that the animal is suitable for these purposes.

4.4.1 Thoroughbred horses

Selective breeding is a crucial aspect of the horse breeding business. Proper breed choice is vital for obtaining the desired results, as each horse breed offers a unique potential in terms of speed, agility, endurance, rideability, and economics. The choice of appropriate breeds is particularly important when using geldings for a wide range of purposes in life.

Table 4. Thoroughbred horses

Kazakh terms	Semantic structure
Argymak	horse + noble breed + capable of developing high speed
Qazanat	horse+noble breed+ strong, fast+ ridden by victorious warriors
Tekezhaumyt	horse+ noble breed + used as a racehorse

Karabayr	horse+ cross between a purebred horse and a Kazakh mare+ excellent working qualities and endurance
Zhaby	horse+Kazakh breed + strong, big, excellent endurance qualities + tolerant to harsh environments+ used for economic purposes
Tobyshaq	horse +high speed, endurance+ excellent for military activities

4.4.2 Fast horses

For the Kazakhs, who were historically nomadic, in ancient times "At" (the riding horse) was an essential means of transportation and the horse's capability to travel rapidly and cover great distances was highly regarded. Its speed has been utilized by people in labor, economic, sports, and military endeavours throughout history and today.

Table 5. Fast horses

Kazakh terms	Semantic structure
Zhorga	horse + a nice, gentle gait + used for riding and racing
Tulpar	a fairy tale winged horse + hardy, strong + ridden by the heroes
Saigulik	horse+ high speed +used as a racehorse
Sanglaq	horse+fast, selected, strong + used as racehorse

Source: Beken Kairatuly. Kazaktyng at begilik onery, (<https://argymaq.kz/archives/3548>)

Table 6. Fairy tale horses

Suyn	a fairy tale horse
Praq	a fairy tale winged horse
Duldul	a fairy tale fast horse

4.5 The periphery of the LSF "Zhylqy"

In the periphery of the LSF "Zhylqy" there are lexical groups containing the phrases with the component 'horse term' related to "Zhylqy toldery" (horse young stock), "Biye" (mare), "At" (gelding).

4.5.1 The lexical-semantic peripheral subgroup of phrases pertaining to "Zhylqy toldery" (young horse stocks). This group incorporates terms for "Kulyn" (foal) denoting their birth season, as well as their feeding and behavioral traits.

"Marqa qulyn" – foal born in winter time; "Kenzhe qulyn" – foal born in May; "Kunqaqty qulyn" – foal that is short of mother's milk; "Zhetym qulyn" – orphaned foal; "Emynshek qulyn" – bottle fed foal; "Tilenshek qulyn" – bottle fed foal that always asks for milk; "Asau qulyn" – skittish foal with wild personality; "Shudan qulyn" – born by different breed mare and stallion.

4.5.2 The lexical-semantic peripheral subgroup of phrases related to "Biye" (mare).

This group comprises phrases with the term "Biye" to express its various characteristics, including fertility or infertility, milk productivity, behavior or misbehavior, and udder characteristics.

Fertility/infertility

Fertile mares

The significance of fertility factor is verbalized by the following phrases:

“*Buaz biye*” – pregnant mare; “*Qulyq biye*” – a 3-4yearsold filly, that gave birth to the 1st foal; “*Qut biye*” – a strong, productive mare, always giving birth to female foals; “*Saba biye*” – a mare, that has large belly and has given birth to many foals; “*Saqa biye*” – an aged mare, that has given birth to 5-6 foals; “*Erte biye*” (*Green mare*) – a mare, namely, a foal or filly, that gets pregnant at an early age and gives birth to a foal; “*Tel biye*” – a mare, that feeds the foal she has given birth the year before because of miscarriage or loss of her foal in the current year; “*Aramza biye*” (*cunning mare*) – a mare that foals in winter. According to Kazakh horse breeding tradition the preferable foaling season is early spring, so that a foal could grow and get stronger by winter; “*Tai biye*” – a one year old foal that is born early in wintertime sometimes gets pregnant at a very early age. (1-year from birth) and gives birth to a foal at the age of two.

Infertile mares

Infertile mares are also linguistically distinguished by the following phrases: “*Tou biye*” – a fat mare, that had miscarriage or barren; “*Qurtyq biye*” – a small sized, low breed mare, giving birth to weak, fragile foals; “*Qysyr biye*” – a barren mare, non pregnant at the end of the breeding period; “*Bedeu biye*” – a barren, sterile mare; “*Sharlangan biye*” – a mare that had miscarriage; “*Tungan biye*” – an infertile mare, because of its obesity.

Lexical subgroup: “Milk productivity”

This subgroup subsumes phrases with “*biye*”, denoting a mare that produces a large amount of milk: “*Mama biye*” – a big sized, well trained, muscular, very clever, strong dairy mare, always giving a high yield of milk; “*Mes biye*” – a strong, cold tolerant mare, producing plenty of milk and giving birth to healthy foals; “*Qundy biye*” – a valuable, strong and hardy breed mare, producing plenty of milk; “*Aqkeul biye*” – a very kind, generous, high yielding mare with a good milk flow.

Mare, producing little or no milk: “*Manersiz biye*” – a mare, producing very little milk; “*Sualgan biye*” – a mare whose milk has dried up; “*Kara kemyk biye*” – a very thin, skinny mare, producing little milk; “*Kara zhelyn biye*” – a mare, that produces little milk because of tough udder; “*Zhasyq biye*” – a low breed mare, underweight, that has low milk productivity; “*Qozhyragan biye*” – a mare, whose milk productivity is gradually decreasing.

Lexical subgroup “Behavior pattern”

Lexical group “Behavior/misbehavior”: “*Zhuas biye*” – a gentle, well-trained mare; “*Naz biye*” – a gentle, reliable, stable mare; “*Tebegen biye*” – a mare, that keeps kicking during milking; “*Asau biye*” – a skittish, untrained mare, that has bad personality; “*Tarpang biye*” – a fearful mare, that gets nervous and excited when frightened; “*Bezer biye*” – a mare, that exhibits aggressive behavior, kicks and bites anyone who comes closer to him; “*Shalkes minezdy biye*” – an untrained, easily distracted, and frightened mare.

Lexical group: “Udder characteristics”

The mare's udder is small, divided into only two lobes, each with a small nipple. “*Shipy emshek biye*” – a mare that has small udder and teats; “*Tar urpily biye*” – a mare that has very thin teat canal and orifice; “*Keng urpily biye*” – a mare that has a wide teat canal and orifice; “*Tik emshek biye*” – a mare that has cylindrical shape of teats; “*Taltaq emshek biye*” – a mare that has opposite directed teats' placement; “*Syngar emshek biye*” – one of two teats has no milk flow; “*Byrtyq emshek biye*” – funnel shaped teats, which cause milking difficulties; “*Tostagan zhelin biye*” – cup shaped udder.

4.5.3 The Lexical-semantic peripheral subgroup of phrases related to “At” (gelding)

Work horses

Depending on the functions performed by “At” (gelding), there are terms in the Kazakh language picture emphasizing different qualities of the horse predominantly used for labor and riding. We unite this group of lexemes under the name “Work horses”:

Beryk at – a strong horse with a well-developed musculature although not predisposed to long term gallop but excellent for trotting slowly on long roads. It is a good draft horse well adapted to all weathers and to carry heavy loads; “*Shobyr at*” – a draft horse for drawing heavy loads and good for farm work; “*Tugyr at*” – a horse excellent for riding, enduring for long distances; “*Mes at*” – a very enduring, big, strong horse, good for heavy agricultural labor; “*Zhetyk at*” – a very sensitive hunting horse. This horse is not used in farm work, so that it doesn’t lose its sensitive abilities; “*Baqal at*” – a horse suitable for riding short distances and a good helper in looking after home livestock; “*Shaban at*” – a lazy, slow animal; “*Epty at*” – a horse good for riding on stony mountainous and uneven roads; “*Ozdyk at*” – a horse belonging to only one person that is adapted to his/her needs; “*Saqa at*” – a 11-12 years old calm and friendly horse that has served long years; “*Mastek*” – a low-breed small obedient horse.

5. Discussion

The archiseme “*Zhylqy*” (horse) serves as the nucleus of the LSF of horse phrases, conveying the field's basic meaning. *The near nucleus/center* is composed of the thematic groups that include horse terms proper: *Horse offspring* (5 terms), *Female horse* (13 terms), “*Aigyr*” (male horse, uncastrated, 7 terms), “*At*” (castrated horse).

The periphery of the semantic field comprises the lexical groups that contain stable phrases denoting various specific features of the horses depending on their function they perform in the life of people and specific qualities they possess, like fertility/infertility (16 lexemes); milk productivity/non productivity (11 lexemes); behavior patterns (7 lexemes); udder characteristics (8 lexemes), horse breed (6 lexemes); ability to move fast (6 lexemes), work horses (11 lexemes).

The thematic group “*Zhylqy toldery*”: The Kazakh culture has classified the life of a foal into four distinct stages: “*Kulyنشak*” (1-1.5 months), “*Kulyن*” (1.5-6 months), “*Zhabagy*” (6-12 months), “*Tai*” and “*Arda*” (1-2 years). During this time, the foal relies solely on its mother's milk for sustenance. Each phase of a foal's life is significant and requires careful attention and appropriate care from humans. A range of names for foals indicate the special responsibility that humans have for them during their first year of life (Borkfelt, 2011). The Kazakhs hold that “*Mal tolden osedi*” (Livestock grows from young), which means that one should take a special care of the young stock.

The thematic group “Female horse” includes 13 terms. The differential features “gender” and “age” are specifically important to the Kazakhs when it concerns the female horse.

The female horses play a pivotal role in their life because the female horse carries and nurtures the future generations of horses and provides milk which has the unique health-improving properties. It is a healthy food, a unique quality product which can reduce or completely prevent the symptoms of many diseases. It strengthens the body, boosts immunity, increases energy and stamina (Zhangabylov, 2015). There is a proverb in Kazakh, which specifies the significance of biye: “*Kedey bolain degen zhygyt, biyesyn satyp at qylar*” – The young man who sells his mare and buys a gelding is going to be poor. The arrival of a female foal is always a happy event with the Kazakhs because it implies the continuation of the reproduction cycle.

The importance and vital function of the female horse in the life of the Kazakhs justifies the need for a clear and precise terminology to distinguish each 2 years of the mare's age during her entire life, and specifies the nature of the responsibility that man assumes for the mare's well-being: “*Qunazhyn*” (2-3 years old); “*Donezhyn*” (3 years old); “*Baital*” (3-4 years old) denotes a maiden filly that hasn't foaled. If they foal in this life period, then they are called: “*Qunazhyn biye*”, “*Donezhyn biye*”, “*Baital biye*” meaning that they have foaled.

The average life expectancy of horses is 25 to 30 years. In the Kazakh language there are special terms for every two year's of age: “*Biye*” 5-6 years; “*Qasabaly biye*” 7-8; “*Sary qaryn biye*” 8-9; “*Kartamys biye*” 10-14; “*Kary biye*” 15-16; “*Zhasagan biye*” 16-19; “*Laqsa biye*” 20 +.

There are special terms for a mare that has foaled for the first time – “*Qoulyq*”, and for a barren mare – non pregnant by the end of the breeding period – “*Qysyraq*” and a mare that has had miscarriage – “*Soital*”.

The multiplicity of terms used to identify the age of female horses highlights the importance of the category of age in the Kazakh context. Age is a crucial factor in determining a horse's ability to reproduce, produce milk, be used for transportation, perform agricultural work, and participate in sports and entertainment activities. The presence of separate terms in the Kazakh language denoting every two years of a mare's life indicates her ability to be reproductive until 20 years of its age. Although the fertility decreases as the mare age increases, the Kazakhs consider that under good conditions of feeding, housing, care and moderate work, especially valuable mares are capable to bring foals up to 20 years of age or more.

Female horses are, practically, multifunctional animals: although their main function is to continue the reproductive cycle, they are omnipresent in many areas of life. They are used for transport, agricultural work, sport, and play. They are excellent for participating in races. Mares successfully compete against their male counterparts and often win (Henry, 2022)

This system is highly informative, with precise and detailed differentiation of female horse terms throughout their lives. The vital characteristics of this animal, its behavior, habits, reproductive abilities and milk productivity are linguistically encoded in an extensive number of phrasal terms which we have categorized into four lexical-semantic subgroups: “Milk productivity”, “Fertility/infertility”, “Behavior/misbehavior”, “Udder characteristics” (40 phrases).

Mare fertility is a “luxury” factor for Kazakhs not only because it meant the increase of the number of livestock of horses, because only a foaled mare can provide milk which is the main ingredient of a healing drink – “*koumys*”. In contrast, infertility is a frustrating issue. Both characteristics find reflection in 10/6 lexemes respectively.

Milk productivity is a highly vital quality in “*Biye*” (mare) that is reflected linguistically in phrases that describe mares with high milking capacity (5 phrases) while low or no milking(7phrases) capacity of mares which is a frustrating issue.

Behavior pattern: Sometimes a mare's poor behavior interferes with her management, training, or performance, which can cause serious problems for owners and milkers. In many cases, a level of mare's milk yield is closely related to her milking behavior. *Udder shape* also plays an essential role in milk yield.

The thematic group “*At*” represents the second highly informative semantic system within the LSF “*Zhylyqy*” that subsumes detailed names specifying horse breed, fast horses, and workhorses.

Kazakhs have a unique reverence for horses, expressed in a saying: “*At beibyt kynde kolik, qyin kunde serik*” – “A horse is a means of transportation in times of peace and a true friend in times of trouble”. Castration of horses results in tamer, human-friendly, and easily manageable horses. Due to their reliability and manageable nature, horses serve in various capacities. The economic and cultural importance of this animal in the Kazakh way of life is reflected by 26 terms in the Kazakh language picture.

The thematic group “*At tuqymy*” (Horse Breed) includes 6 terms. Each breed is adapted to perform different functions (**speed, agility, endurance, rideability and economic**). For ex.: “*Zhaby*” – a strong, big, tolerant to harsh environments horse of Kazakh breed with excellent endurance qualities widely used for economic purposes; “*Argymak*” – a horse of noble breed, capable of developing high speed; “*Qazanat*” – a noble breed strong, fast, war horse ridden by a victorious warrior; “*Tekezhaumyt*” – a noble breed used as a racehorse, “*Karabayr*” – a cross between a purebred horse and a Kazakh mare has excellent working qualities and endurance.

In the Kazakh language very often “*At*” is substituted by the naming of its breed: For ex.: “*Kunderding kuninde Aidarbek degen joldasymnyng qara argymagyn surap alyp, Mortaidy alyp qashtym*” – One day I borrowed my friend Aidarbek’s *black argymak* and stole Mortai (the name of the hero’s sweetheart who he kidnapped) (Shanai, 2023). *Nagyز saigulik eken. Bundai saigulikti kormegen Madidyng kozi zhainap ketty.* – It was a real *saigulyk!*(a super fast horse). On seeing a *real saigulik* for the first time in his life Mady’s eyes got filled with astonishment and delight.

- *Al, Mady, dostym, tulpar seniky!* – Well, Mady, my friend! *The tulpar* is yours!

The peripheral subgroup of LSF “At” (Work horse) subsumes 10 phrasal terms (“beryk at”, “shobyr at”, “mess at”, “tugyr at”, “ozdyk at”, “baqal at”, “epty at”, “mastek at”, “saqa at”, “shaban at”) denote various physiological and functional characteristics of horses.

The fairy tale, mythological horse terms: “Suyn”, “Praq”, “Dul-Dul”.

Horses have commonly featured as heroic creatures in myths and legends across diverse cultures. In Kazakh folklore, an enchanting sea horse named “*Suyn*” (sea stallion, sea filly/mare) is the focus of one such myth. As per the legend, sea horses reside in the deep seas and intermittently emerge onto the shore to fatten up. Experienced horse breeders send fillies to the coast in advance aiming to impregnate at least one of them with a sea stallion. The resulting foal usually develops into a strong and powerful adult, frequently becoming the fastest horse on Earth (Kondybai, 2013).

6. Conclusion

The world, in which we live, with all its observable distinctions, exists independently of language. It is a very complex but objectively structured collection of entities, including people, animals, plants, and events. For each of these entities, language has a specific word. Every language models the surrounding world in a way that makes it possible for the members of the relevant speech community to function in it properly.

The crucial role of horses and their omnipresence in the life of the Kazakh people have found expression in the language and in the course of the centuries-old practice of horse breeding the Kazakh language has accumulated a vast layer of words and phrases. A wide range of terms attests to the fact that historically, the Kazakhs drew their sustenance from the horse, by exploiting it for meat and products like milk, hide, by using it in the battles to defend their lands, agricultural labor and transportation. All this triggered a high communicative need to distinguish between the many properties and qualities of this animal, and, accordingly, there are many terms for stages of their age, productivity/non-

productivity in terms of reproductive capacity and milk yield, behavioral characteristics of female species, speed characteristics of the male species, etc. The communicative need affects the structure of the lexicon as a whole. Each term is used to communicate informatively about the animal. For the Kazakhs it was unacceptable to allow communicative errors in the transmission of information about this animal. The multiplicity of terms ensures the accuracy of the transfer of information about each distinctive feature of the animal and meet the communicative need thereby supporting efficient communication. This idea was suggested by many scholars, who argued that the terms in any language “must, to a certain extent, depend upon the chief interests of a people” and vocabulary of a language may be looked upon as a complex inventory of all the ideas, interests, and occupations that take up the attention of the community (Boas, 1911).

Each horse term within the LSG “*Zhylqy*” has its allotted place and carries its own meaning. Each term comprehensively reflects the function of this animal it fulfills and the role it plays in the life of the Kazakhs. The existence of multiple names to the same animal “*Zhylqy*” suggests the specific responsibility of the Kazakhs for the animal’s welfare throughout its life and emphasizes its unique importance in their lives.

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